

GREEN FOOTPRINTS FROM BENGKULU: UMB'S KHDTK COLLABORATION AS THE FOUNDATION FOR ENVIRONMENTAL GOVERNANCE REFORM

Rekho Adriadi¹, Susiyanto², Rosyidin³

^{1,2,3}Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Universitas Muhammadiyah Bengkulu

*Corresponding Author: rekhoadriadi@umb.ac.id

ABSTRACT

Environmental sustainability issues at the local level have become increasingly urgent amid growing ecological pressures and weak bureaucratic capacity to integrate green governance principles into public policy. This study analyzes the role of Muhammadiyah University of Bengkulu's (UMB) Special Purpose Forest Area (KHDTK) as an innovative multi-stakeholder collaborative model for green governance. Using a qualitative approach through in-depth interviews, field observations, and document analysis, this study examines how UMB's KHDTK contributes to environmental governance reform in Bengkulu, particularly through strengthening research, conservation, sustainable ecotourism, and local community empowerment. The findings show that UMB's KHDTK serves as a governance laboratory that connects academics, local government, and communities in building more responsive, evidence-based environmental governance practices. The collaboration developed not only produces technical innovations in forest ecosystem management but also influences regional policy-making by providing scientific data, replicable empowerment models, and conservation practices. This study confirms that strengthening collaboration between universities and local stakeholders is key to accelerating environmental governance reform at the regional level, while also promoting the realization of sustainable development agenda in Bengkulu.

Keywords: Environmental Innovation, Green Governance, KHDTK, Multi-Stakeholder Collaboration, Public Policy.